

STORIES THAT MATTER: EXPLORING FINANCIAL MATHEMATICS WITH COMIC BOOKS AND VIDEO PRODUCTION

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ABSTRACT

This report describes the activities developed, including the production of comic strips and videos, during financial mathematics classes with second-year students in integrated technical courses (Informatics, Commerce, and Electronics) throughout the years 2022, 2023, and 2024 at the Federal Institute of Rio Grande do Norte, Natal Campus – North Zone. The classes were divided into groups of four. Each group was responsible for one of the following topics: Learning to calculate income tax, Inflation or deflation: which is worse, Real Estate Financing: Amortization using the SAC system, Real Estate Financing: Amortization using the Price system, Fixed Income I, Variable Income, Credit card interest: Do you know how to calculate it?, and Fixed Income II. The comic strips could be developed using the Pixton tool (<https://www.pixton.com/welcome>) and the videos produced should be published on YouTube in unlisted mode. The conclusion of the work was carried out in a thematic class called "Mathematical Café," where we formed a discussion circle to talk about the difficulties and lessons learned from carrying out the work. The results obtained from these activities were satisfactory, as the students reported that the knowledge acquired would be applied to their lives outside of school, both because of the importance of the theme and the way the activities were developed. Furthermore, carrying out these activities led to the creation of a research project that aims to create a calculator-style application that performs financial calculations.

Keywords: Financial Mathematics, Comic Books, Video Production, Mathematics Education.

1. INTRODUCTION

Financial mathematics is a branch of mathematics that studies concepts related to commercial operations, such as amortizations, interest calculations on loans or financing, percentage increases or discounts on products or services, gains or losses on investments, among others.

Teixeira and Neto (2016, p. 2) highlight that:

Financial transactions are part of people's daily lives, especially in their consumption habits, purchasing power, and installment plans that can compromise people's budgets. These "consumers," in turn, have not always been prepared by school to understand them and, consequently, do not stop to think about where the financial information comes from and how it is processed; they simply pay without understanding or sometimes without questioning.

Given the above, and the importance of this topic, which is characterized by knowledge of the main financial operations, the need to address financial mathematics topics in a different way became apparent. In our case, the main objective was to develop student learning using comic strips and video production on the following topics: Learning to calculate income tax, Inflation or deflation: which is worse, Real Estate Financing: Amortization using the SAC system, Real Estate Financing: Amortization using the Price system, Fixed Income I, Variable Income, Credit card interest: Do you know how to calculate it?, and Fixed Income II.

Thus, the objective of this work is to describe the activities and experiences lived by the students and the teacher throughout the years 2022, 2023 and 2024, during mathematics classes, especially financial mathematics classes.

2. THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

According to the National Curriculum Parameters (PCN, 2000), it is a fundamental part of teaching practices for the teacher to present Mathematics as knowledge that fosters the development of reasoning, the ability to express and organize ideas, and, moreover, the imagination of students when faced with problem situations. The National Common Curriculum Base (BNCC, 2018) corroborates this idea by highlighting that it is in high school that students develop useful skills to solve real problems by applying mathematical concepts that arise throughout their lives. Given what has been presented by official documents, which generally address basic education, it is clear that mathematics should be developed in a way that connects students to their daily lives, with the main objective being "the improvement of the student as a human being, including ethical formation and the development of intellectual autonomy and critical thinking" (LDB 9394/96, p. 27).

Financial mathematics is a great option to develop in a way that brings mathematics closer to students' daily lives. This area of mathematics is dedicated to the study of financial operations: such as the calculation of simple and compound interest, the comparison of investments, the analysis of financing and loans, as well as the calculation of installments and amortization. According to Santos (2023, p. 25), financial mathematics has great potential to

be developed starting from students' experiences, since they come into contact with graphs, tables, and interest rates daily through the media. Silveira, Carvalho, and Sobrinho (2020, p. 51-685) corroborate this idea when they highlight that the use of financial mathematics associated with students' daily lives contributes to the preparation of more critical and conscious individuals in the exercise of citizenship in matters of finance.

Regarding the teaching-learning process of mathematics, the use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) has been highlighted. Studies indicate that the integration of technological tools helps in visualizing abstract concepts, promoting greater engagement and motivation among students. Furthermore, with the use of ICTs, it is possible for classes to be more attractive, facilitating the construction of knowledge in a more dynamic and interactive way. However, for these technologies to be effectively incorporated into the educational environment, it is essential to invest in the continuous training of teachers and ensure adequate infrastructure in schools, as highlighted by Camillo (2019). Sharing the same thought regarding the use of ICTs in mathematics classes, we emphasize...

[...] that the use of ICTs in education is extremely important, particularly in mathematics classes. However, we cannot forget that ICTs do not replace the teacher-student-knowledge relationship in the teaching-learning process, but are a didactic resource whose objective is to facilitate learning and enhance students' knowledge in a dynamic way. (SANTOS, 2017, np)

Thus, it is clear that the use of ICTs plays a fundamental role in the teaching-learning process, as it contributes to a more direct relationship between teacher-student-knowledge, providing greater interaction and engagement in classes, and also enables the development of more dynamic and attractive classes.

3. METHODOLOGY

The activities described in this work were developed with 2nd-year high school students from the Integrated Technical Courses in Informatics, Electronics, and Commerce at the Federal Institute of Rio Grande do Norte, Natal Zona Norte *Campus*.

The approach to financial mathematics in the classroom was developed in two phases. The first phase was dedicated to working on the theoretical concepts of percentages, simple and compound interest, discounts, and financial updating (present value and future value) through lectures using a whiteboard, markers, projector, Excel spreadsheets, and a scientific calculator. The second phase was dedicated to the production of comic strips and educational videos made

by the students. In this stage, we explored additional topics directly related to the students' daily lives, making learning more meaningful. This knowledge not only enriched their academic training but also played an essential role in preparing them for their personal and professional lives.

In the second phase, the classes were divided into groups of four. Each group was responsible for one of the following topics: Learning to calculate income tax, Inflation or deflation: which is worse, Real Estate Financing: Amortization using the SAC system, Real Estate Financing: Amortization using the Price system, Fixed Income I, Variable Income, Credit card interest: Do you know how to calculate it?, and Fixed Income II.

For the creation of the comics, students were advised to use the Pixton platform ¹. This tool is used to create comic strips. It has a full paid version, but also a free version. A tutorial on how to use this tool was provided. Students could also use other tools to complete the work. The comics should have a context with a beginning, middle, and end, addressing one of the themes mentioned above.

Figure 1: Pixton tool page

Source: <https://www.pixton.com/welcome> (2025)

For the production of the videos, students were advised to upload them to YouTube in unlisted mode. They could record using a white square, slides, or the hand-drawn technique. The videos should have a context with a beginning, middle, and end, addressing one of the themes mentioned above, and should last between 10 and 20 minutes.

¹<https://www.pixton.com/welcome>

Thirty days were allocated for the completion of the project. During this period, students could contact the teacher to clarify any doubts and present the activity plan with the results of their research on the proposed topic. If the plan was not adequate, the teacher offered suggestions for improvement. This process continued until the project was finished. The conclusion of this activity took place in a thematic class called "Mathematical Coffee Break." In this class, we held a discussion about the project, where experiences, difficulties, and lessons learned from completing the activity were shared. This moment was also marked by a lovely coffee break organized by the class and the teacher.

4. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

This work highlights the importance of addressing additional topics in financial mathematics through comics and video production. Students reported learning how to calculate a worker's income tax, credit card interest, and the calculations involved in financing a property using the Price Table or the SAC system. Thus, by establishing connections between financial mathematics and students' everyday situations, the learning had a significant impact on their academic and social lives, making them more aware and prepared to make decisions in situations involving money.

Based on these activities developed at the Federal Institute of Rio Grande do Norte, Natal Zona Norte *Campus*, a research project emerged that aims to create a calculator-style application that performs financial calculations. Furthermore, it is intended that this application will be available to the entire community. Therefore, carrying out these activities proved very important for both the teacher and the students, as learning was developed in a way that differed from the traditional model. In conclusion, the results obtained were satisfactory, as we achieved more objectives than expected at the end of the project.

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